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Unwana-abasi S. Udoh; Ubong Okon Iyoho

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Fuel Subsidy Removal Policy and Its Toll on the Living Standard of Rural People of the Oil Producing Communities in Niger-Delta Region of Nigeria: A Case of Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

The study sets out to survey the fuel subsidy removal policy and its toll on the living standard of rural people of the oil producing communities of Niger-Delta region of Nigeria on the Gulf of Guinea, with focus on Akwa Ibom State. The Community development theory by Allison Tan (2009) and Empowerment theory by Staples (1990) were adopted in the study. Qualitative survey research design was also adopted and primary and secondary methods of data collection were used for enquiry; three subsidiary objectives were set, including to find out the motivating factors of government towards implementing fuel subsidy removal policy at this critical moment in Nigeria; three research questions and three null hypotheses were created to guide the study. The findings showed that there are some serious motivating factors of government towards implementing fuel subsidy removal policy at this critical moment in Nigeria. It was recommended, among others, that the Federal Government should be transparent, fair and accountable to citizens in utilizing the huge sum of money, Four Hundred Billion Naira (N400b) saved monthly by the Presidency from the commencement of the fuel subsidy removal. This will justify the fact that there were some serious and positive motivating factors towards implementing fuel subsidy removal policy at this critical moment in Nigeria, which according to the government, included serious allegations of corruption and mismanagement of subsidy funds.

Keywords: Fuel Subsidy, Fuel Subsidy Removal Policy, Living Standard, Rural People, Oil Producing Communities and Niger Delta Region.

1. Background to the Study

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Nigeria is a heterogeneous, multi-populated and multi-dimensional country in the African continent with thirty-six (36) States, including the Federal Capital Territory in Abuja. The people of the Niger-Delta and their communities form the bulk of the oil producing area of the region which also feeds the entire country and beyond with crude oil and other essential mineral resources. This research is a participant study intended to focus on the living standard or the cost of living of the people of the Niger-Delta during the post fuel subsidy removal by the Tinubu administration on May 29, 2023 immediately following the swearing into office of the President.

Several scholars and indeed, the World Bank have observed that in Nigeria, the price of petrol is considered as a major driver of the cost of living as it is used by all including small businesses and many households given the unstable electricity supply. Therefore, any increase in fuel price could directly and immediately impact the prices of goods and services across the country. There is also the psychological effect that it tends to have because of the strong sentiment attached to cheap and affordable petrol by Nigerians. When petrol prices increase, small businesses tend to raise their prices to cover the increased cost of operation. This can make it difficult for people to afford basic necessities, thereby, leading to a decrease in the standard of living and contributing to poverty and inequality. However, previous attempts to remove the PMS subsidy had mostly been accompanied by hoarding and general scarcity which invariably amplified the impact of the price increase beyond just the subsidy removal.

In all, the relationship between petrol price increases, inflation, and the cost of living in Nigeria is complex and multifaceted. While petrol price deregulation can contribute to higher costs of living and inflation, the impact can be moderated if complemented with effective policies and well-thought out implementation strategy. The Nigerian economy has been subsidized in various ways for many years and this includes fuel, education, electricity, forex, etc. Fuel subsidies began in the 1970s and became institutionalized in 1977, following the promulgation of the Price Control Act which made it illegal for some products (including petrol) to be sold above the regulated price. While the concept of subsidy itself is noble, its administration in Nigeria has been plagued with serious allegations of corruption and mismanagement. Though the Tinubu led government has removed the subsidy, it seems it is not prepared to show sufficient

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concern on how to tame the tide of continual increases in the prices of petroleum products by the independent marketers, particularly those in the petroleum sub-sector. This situation has brought untold hardship on the entire populace in the country, hence, the reason to embark on this participant research to unravel the impact of fuel subsidy removal on the living standards of the people of Akwa Ibom State in the Niger-Delta Region of Nigeria.

2. Statement of the Problem

From the inception of the present administration led by President Ahmed Bola Tinubu, and following his somewhat hasty pronouncement of the fuel subsidy removal immediately after his swearing into office as the President of Nigeria, there has been a turn-around in the living standards of people in Nigeria. Life has no longer been bearable. The cost of living has astronomically skyrocketed beyond lips and bounds and there is serious devaluation of the naira. In other words, the value of the naira has practically been reduced to a standard where so much of it has to chase very little quantity of goods. The independent petroleum marketers have taken so much advantage of the situation by increasing fuel prices from N250 to the present N680 per liter. Udoh (2023) laments that due to subsidy removal, prices of fuel were freely determined by Independent Marketers in different states of the federation between N488 and N600 as at few days after the inception of this administration. In Akwa Ibom State, for instance, petrol was sold at about N535 at the NNPC Mega Station, Uyo.

According to Blackgold (2021), the Nigerian economy has been subsidized in various ways for many years and this included fuel, education, electricity, forex, etc. Fuel subsidies began in the 1970s and became institutionalized in 1977, following the promulgation of the Price Control Act which made it illegal for some products (including petrol) to be sold above the regulated price. While the concept of subsidy itself is noble, its administration in Nigeria has been plagued with serious allegations of corruption and mismanagement.

Thirteen years after diesel was deregulated, kerosene subsidy was removed in 2016. However, the subsidy on Petroleum Motor Spirit (PMS) has proven to be the biggest challenge to the managers of the Nigerian economy. On an annual basis, a

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substantial portion of the national inflow is committed to funding the subsidy scheme. Of course, there are good reasons for the astronomical growth in subsidy amount - price of crude oil in the international market, volume of PMS consumed albeit debatable, and Naira devaluation are some of the drivers. In view of the significance of the amount committed to funding the subsidy regime, there is a need to have a close look at this scheme.

It is important also to ensure that the most vulnerable population (in our own case the oil producing region, the Niger-Delta Region of Nigeria) is protected from any negative impact of subsidy removal and at the same time secure the necessary support required to make this happen. At present, from a personal participatory market survey and an on-the-spot enquiries by the researchers in the second week of November, 2023, it was startling that the most staple food for even a common man (in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States) as garri was sold at N150.00 (one hundred and fifty naira) per cup; beans cost N250.00 (two hundred and fifty naira) per cup; noddle such as indomie, which is basically food for the children, students and the poor masses (particularly, the hungry man size) was sold at N450.00 and N500.00 per pack, respectively; then, rice which is seen as a commodity for rich was sold at N320.00 (three hundred and twenty naira) per cup. A 50 kg bag of rice costs between N53,000.00 to N56,000.00 depending on the brand.

Furthermore, at present, the official fuel price has increased from N680.00 to between N700.00 and N730.00 depending on fuel stations, while black market price has skyrocketed to N1,200.00 or N1,300.00. A kilo of gas has risen to N1,000.00 and N1,200.00, respectively. The prices of male motor bikes jumped to N600,000.00 to N650,000.00 while the Ladies bike went to N900,000.00 and N1,000,000.00 each depending on the make. Transport fares generally have gone up. Some distances now are covered with a 100% increase in transport fares or more. The above presentations are the current market realities in both Akwa Ibom and Cross River States which are as a result of incessant fuel price increases which are predicated on the recent fuel subsidy removal policy of government. Based on the above analyses, farmers and market men and women seem to have no choice than to sell their goods exorbitantly in order to realize their capitals and also make gains.

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3. Objectives of the Study

While the main Objective of this study was to carry out a survey on fuel subsidy removal policy and its toll on the living standard of rural people of the oil producing communities in Niger-Delta region of Nigeria on the Gulf of Guinea: a case of Akwa Ibom State; the subsidiary objectives included:

- i. To find out the motivating factors of government towards the implementation of fuel subsidy removal policy at this critical moment in Nigeria.
- ii. To evaluate the resultant effects of fuel price hike on the lifestyle of the people of Akwa Ibom and State.
- iii. To ascertain whether the devaluation of the naira has affected the living standard of the rural people of Akwa Ibom State in Nigeria.

4. Research Questions

Based on the above objectives, the following research questions were asked to enable the researchers to elicit answers from the respondents:

- i. What are the motivating factors of government towards implementing fuel subsidy removal policy at this critical moment in Nigeria?
- ii. What are the resultant effects of fuel price hike on the lifestyle of the people of Akwa Ibom and State?
- iii. Can it be ascertained whether the devaluation of the naira has affected the living standard of the rural people of Akwa Ibom State in Nigeria?

5. Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses (Ho) were formulated to aid the research:

- i. There appears to be some motivating factors of government towards implementing fuel subsidy removal policy at this critical moment in Nigeria.
- ii. There tends to be several resultant effects of fuel price hike on the lifestyle of the people of Akwa Ibom State.
- iii. It can most likely be ascertained that the devaluation of the naira has affected the living standard of the rural people of Akwa Ibom State in Nigeria.

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6. Operationalization of Concepts

The concepts used in this research were operationalized to suit the study. They may mean other things elsewhere or in other contexts. The concepts operationalized include:

i. **Fuel Subsidy:** Fuel subsidies began in the 1970s and became institutionalized in 1977, following the promulgation of the Price Control Act which made it illegal for some products (including petrol) to be sold above the regulated price. While the concept of subsidy itself is noble, its administration in Nigeria has been plagued with serious allegations of corruption and mismanagement.

ii. **Fuel Subsidy Removal Policy:** A policy is generally referred to a plan of action agreed or chosen by a political party or a business organization, etc. to serve as a compass or guiding principle in the day-to-day activities of the party or business. It may also refer to a principle that one believes in, that influences how one behaves.

iii. **Living Standard:** Living standard or Standard of living is the level of income, comforts and services available, generally applied to a society or location, rather than to an individual. Standard of living is relevant because it is considered to contribute to an individual's quality of life. Standard of living is generally concerned with objective metrics outside an individual's personal control, such as economic, societal, political and environmental matters – such things that an individual might consider when evaluating where to live in the world, or when assessing the success of economic policy.

iv. **Rural People or Rural Communities:** There are many types of environments in which humans live. The majority of people in the world and in the United States live in urban settings such as cities and suburban neighbourhoods because of the greater number of resources and opportunities afforded to people there. A smaller percentage, however, still live in **rural communities** around the world. What is a rural community? The rural living definition is one that changes depending on several different variables.

v. **Oil Producing Communities:** Oil Producing Communities here is a compound word. For the sake of clarity, it is divided into two categories, namely:

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- a) Oil producing Communities in Nigeria;
- b) Oil producing Communities in the Niger-Delta.

It is intended that both communities be ex-rayed in this study for proper information and guidance.

Oil Producing Communities in Nigeria

Nigeria is a major oil-producing country, and the oil industry plays a significant role in its economy. The main oil-producing regions in Nigeria include:

- a) **Niger Delta Region:** This is the primary oil-producing region in Nigeria, accounting for the majority of the country's crude oil output. States in the Niger Delta include Delta, Bayelsa, Rivers, Akwa Ibom, Cross River, Edo, and Ondo.
- b) **Akwa Ibom State:** Akwa Ibom is one of the top oil-producing states in Nigeria.
- c) **Rivers State:** Another key player in Nigeria's oil industry, Rivers State is home to several oil and gas facilities.
- d) **Delta State:** Delta State is an important oil-producing state, with numerous oil wells and facilities.
- e) **Bayelsa State:** As one of the States in the heart of the Niger Delta, Bayelsa is a significant contributor to Nigeria's oil production.

Oil Producing Communities in Niger-Delta

The Niger-Delta region in Nigeria is known for its significant oil production. The major oil-producing States in the Niger-Delta include:

- a) **Delta State:** This state is a major oil-producing state with several oil and gas fields.
- b) **Rivers State:** Another key player in Nigeria's oil industry, Rivers State is home to various oil wells and facilities.
- c) **Bayelsa State:** This state is at the core of the Niger Delta and is a significant contributor to Nigeria's oil output.
- d) **Akwa Ibom State:** With its offshore oil fields, Akwa Ibom is also a major player in the oil and gas sector.
- e) **Edo State:** While not located directly in the Niger Delta, Edo State hosts some oil-producing communities.

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f) **Ondo State:** Similar to Edo, Ondo State has some oil-producing areas contributing to Nigeria's overall oil production.

Some of the key oil-producing communities in the Niger Delta include:

- a) **Port Harcourt:** As one of the largest cities in the Niger Delta, Port Harcourt is a major hub for oil and gas activities. It hosts several oil companies and is a significant center for economic and industrial activities.
- b) **Warri:** Located in Delta State, Warri is another important oil-producing community in the Niger Delta. It has oil refineries, petrochemical plants, and serves as a major economic center in the region.
- c) **Bonny Island:** This island, situated in Rivers State, is home to the Bonny oil terminal and liquefied natural gas (LNG) facilities. It is a critical location for the export of oil and gas resources.
- d) **Yenagoa:** Yenagoa is the capital of Bayelsa State and is in close proximity to oil-producing areas. It has experienced significant development due to the presence of the oil industry.
- e) **Ogoni Land:** Ogoni land, inhabited by the Ogoni people, has been a focal point for discussions on environmental degradation and social issues associated with oil production. The Ogoni people have raised concerns about the impact of oil activities on their communities.

These communities, among others in the Niger Delta, play a crucial role in Nigeria's oil and gas sector. However, they also face challenges such as environmental pollution, community displacement, and inadequate infrastructure. The issues in the Niger Delta have led to activism and calls for better resource management and environmental protection.

vi. **Niger Delta Region:** The Niger Delta is the delta of the Niger River sitting directly on the Gulf of Guinea on the Atlantic Ocean in Nigeria. It is located within nine coastal southern Nigerian states, which include all six states from the South-South geopolitical zone, one state (Ondo) from South West geopolitical zone and two states (Abia and Imo) from South East geopolitical zone.

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vii. **Akwa Ibom State:** Akwa Ibom State is a state in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria on the east by Cross River State, on the west by Rivers State and Abia State, and on the south by the Atlantic Ocean. The state takes its name from the Qua Iboe River which bisects the state before flowing into the Bight of Bonny. Akwa Ibom was split from Cross River State in 1987 with Uyo as its capital and 31 other local government areas. Of the 36 states of Nigeria, Akwa Ibom is the 30th Largest in area and fifteenth most populous with an estimated population of nearly 5.5 million as of 2016.

viii. **The Gulf of Guinea:** The Gulf of Guinea is the north-easternmost part of the tropical Atlantic Ocean from Cape Lopez in Gabon, north and west to Cape Palmas in Liberia. Null Island, defined as the intersection of the Equator and Prime Meridian (zero degrees latitude and longitude), is in the gulf. Among the many rivers that drain into the Gulf of Guinea are the Niger and the Volta. The coastline on the gulf includes the Bight of Benin and the Bight of Bonny. The origin of the name Guinea is thought to be an area in the region, although the specifics are disputed. Bovill (1995) gives a thorough description;

The name "Guinea" is still attached to the names of three countries in Africa: Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, and Equatorial Guinea, as well as New Guinea in Melanesia. Geographically, the main river dispersing its waters in the gulf is the Niger River. Different definitions of the geographic limits of the Gulf of Guinea are given; the International Hydrographic Organization defines the southwest extent of the Gulf of Guinea as "B line from Cape Lopez (0°37'S8°43'E), in Gabon, northwestward to Ihléu Gago Coutinho (Ilhéu das Rôlas) (0°01'S6°32'E); and thence a line from Ihléu Gago Coutinho northwestward to Cape Palmas (4°22'N7°44'W), in Liberia.

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7. Theoretical Framework

The study adopted two set of theories to substantiate the research. These theories include:

- a. Community Development Theory
- b. Empowerment Theory

Community Development Theory was propounded by Allison Tan in 2009. It is the most practical framework for social workers seeking lasting change for individuals and the communities and societies in which they live. It focuses on the centrality of oppressed people in the process of overcoming externally imposed social problems (Allison Tan, 2009). This theory is a community development work because by the mere fact of the definition, it speaks for itself. The theory could adapt to other disciplines like Neighbourhood Development, and so on.

Empowerment Theory on the other hand, refers to the experience of personal growth and an improvement in self-definition that occurs as a result of the development of capabilities and proficiencies (Staples 1990). Another definition suggests that empowerment is a combination of personal strengths, initiative, and natural helping systems to bring about change (Perkins & Zimmerman, 1995). This theory can be applied to community development by empowering the people within the community to develop their own community. The theory can adapt to other disciplines like Sociology. It was spearheaded by Staples in 1990.

Application of the Theories to the Study

To begin with, Allison Tan in 2009 in his community development theory, has postulated the ideal situation for the downtrodden and the oppressed people and communities the world over as he identified that very theory as the most practical framework for societies if a lasting change was to be achieved. In his words, "Community Development Theory is the most practical framework for social workers seeking lasting change for individuals and the communities and societies in which they live. It focuses on the centrality of oppressed people in the process of overcoming externally imposed social problems" (Tan, 2009).

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But, rather than achieve the obvious, as the author anticipated or envisaged, the oppressed people and communities are rather made to continue in their oppressed state or, worse still, they are made to degenerate to worst social conditions than the externally imposed social problems meted on them. Take for instance, there is no much or preponderance of evidence in terms of development in Eket, Ibeno, Esit Eket, Eastern Obolo LGAs of Akwa Ibom State despite the fact that these are the core oil producing LGAs in the State. To say the least, in Ibeno, Esit Eket, Eastern Obolo LGAs, there are no roads. Each of the three LGAs have only one access road which also serve as the exit route. Imagine what would happen if there should be any serious crisis that occur in these places.

Furthermore, it is difficult to say that a Multinational Corporation like the Exxon Mobil Unlimited is situated in Ibeno as the entire community is enshroud with shackles called houses where people live and have their livelihood. There is only one major road in the area which was an intervention by the government of the last administration; otherwise, the place would have been in a total shamble as the few streets there are almost impassable, particularly during the rainy seasons that the entire communities will be submerged by flood.

In Eket, one may describe it as a mini city. This is as a result of the Eket Remodeling Project of the previous government in the state. There is no particular infrastructure put in place by Exxon Mobil, except the popular Mobile Airstrip which only serves the elitists purposes by enhancing the daily movements (landing and taking off) of the foreign experts to and from their base and headquarters in Lagos and Abuja, the Nigeria's Federal Capital City. But, day in and day out, an influx of foreigners and strangers are usually observed coming in to assume one leadership position or the other in the company.

Aside from the company's neglect on corporate social responsibility and human capital development, the entire business environments are in a mess. Aquatic lives and farm lands are destroyed due to oil spillage; the roofs of people's houses are corroded because of gas flaring; also hampered by constant gas flaring is the air around those communities. This is to say the least.

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Like Allison Tan asserted, this theory is supposed to be a community development work because by the mere fact of the definition it speaks for itself. But it is not so because the players only exploit both the human and material resources in the communities and walk away. The oil producing communities in Akwa Ibom State in Nigeria on the Gulf of Guinea only continue to serve as the goose that lay the golden eggs for all others to eat. There is so much injustice meted on these communities.

If Empowerment Theory (Staples, 1990; Perkins & Zimmerman, 1995) was to be followed which refers to the experience of personal growth and an improvement in self-definition that occurs as a result of the development of capabilities and proficiencies, there would have been a rapid development of the oil producing communities in the sense that the citizens of the areas would have been empowered by this company, thereby translating that into their community development. Another definition suggests that empowerment is a combination of personal strengths, initiative, and natural helping systems to bring about change. It can be imagined how frustrated these authors will be when they observe that this theory cannot be applied to community development by empowering the people within the community to develop their own community as it was supposed to be.

8. Methodology

This study adopted the qualitative survey research design because the study involves longitudinal investigations. A longitudinal survey study involves examining survey responses over a certain timeframe to investigate whether there is any change in your variables of interest. In such a design, your survey needs to be administered at least twice – once at the start and at the end of the timeframe. You may also opt to administer it in the middle of the timeframe as well (ABS, 2021). As such, both primary and secondary methods of enquiry were made use of. The primary data were basically from personal observations and interviews, while the secondary data were drawn from relevant text books, journals, newspapers and the internet.

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9. Literature Review

The issue of length as a requirement by the publisher is a major challenge to this research. But, nevertheless, it behooves on the researchers to limit their literature review to the works of Udoh (2023) and Blackgold (2021) who are seen to have provided sufficient ingredients that can boost this study to the satisfactions of both the authors and readers as well. Before considering the issues bothering on fuel subsidy in Nigeria as expatiated by Blackgold, lets first look at the history of fuel price increases as tabulated by Udoh (2023).

The Statistical History of Fuel Price Hike in Nigeria

i.	Gowon:	1973	6k to 8.45k	(40.8%)
ii.	Murtala:	1976	8.45k to 9k	(0.59%)
iii.	Obasanjo:	October, 1978	9k to 15.3k	(70%)
iv.	Shagari:	April 20, 1982	15.3k to 20k	(30.71%)
v.	Babangida:	March 31, 1986	20k to 39.5k	(97.5%)
vi.	Babangida:	April 10, 1988	39.5k to 42k	(6.33%)
vii.	Babangida:	January 1, 1989	42k to 60k	Private vehicles
viii.	Babangida:	December 19, 1989	Moved to uniform price of 60k	(42.86%)
ix.	Babangida:	March 6, 1991	60k to 70k	(16.67%)
x.	Shonekan:	November 8, 1993	70k to N5	(61.4%)
xi.	Abacha:	November 22, 1993	Petrol price dropped from N5 to N3.25k	(361.54%)
xii.	Abubakar:	December 20, 1998	N11 to N25	(127.27%)
xiii.	Abubakar:	January 6, 1999	N25 to N20	(-20%)
xiv.	Obasanjo:	January 1, 2002	N22 to N26	(18.18%)
xv.	Obasanjo:	June-October, 2003	N26 to N42	(23.08%)
xvi.	Obasanjo:	May 29, 2004	N50	(19.05%)
xvii.	Obasanjo:	August 25, 2004	N22 to N26	(30%)
xviii.	Obasanjo:	May 2, 2007	N75	(15.38%)
xix.	Ya'Adua:	June, 2007	N65	(-15.38%)
xx.	Jonathan:	January 1, 2012	B/w N138 and N250	(112.3 284.82%)
xxi.	Buhari	May 29, 2015	N250-N350	(284.82 to 293.82 %)
xxii.	Tinubu:	May 31, 2023	<i>Due to sub sidy removal, prices of fuel were determined by Independent Marketers in different states of the federation b/w N488 and N600. In Akwa Ibom State, it was sold at about N535 at the NNPC Mega Station. As at the second week of November, 2023 fuel was selling between N700 and N750 in Akwa Ibom State.</i>	

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Fuel Subsidy in Nigeria - Issues, Challenges and the Way Forward

There are several challenges that stem from funding fuel subsidy in Nigeria. Without intending to discuss them, these include unsustainable financial cost of subsidy, economic distortion, smuggling, endemic corruption, investment and climate change commitments. The Nigerian economy has been subsidized in various ways for many years and this includes fuel, education, electricity, forex, etc. Fuel subsidies began in the 1970s and became institutionalized in 1977, following the promulgation of the Price Control Act which made it illegal for some products (including petrol) to be sold above the regulated price. While the concept of subsidy itself is noble, its administration in Nigeria has been plagued with serious allegations of corruption and mismanagement.

Thirteen years after diesel was deregulated, kerosene subsidy was removed in 2016. However, the subsidy on Petroleum Motor Spirit (PMS) has proven to be the biggest challenge to the managers of the Nigerian economy. On an annual basis, a substantial portion of the national inflow is committed to funding the subsidy scheme. Of course there are good reasons for the astronomical growth in subsidy amount - price of crude oil in the international market, volume of PMS consumed albeit debatable, and Naira devaluation are some of the drivers. In view of the significance of the amount committed to funding the subsidy regime, there is a need to have a close look at this scheme.

We started off this discussion with a focus on the challenges of retaining fuel subsidy in its current form and thereafter, examine the associated economic issues. We have dwelt more on the solution as most key stakeholders agree that the subsidy regime needs to go, it is clearly not sustainable in its current form. In this paper, we have put together a simple and practical solution to this long standing problem and a backup solution which could serve as a stop-gap measure towards full removal. The dual objectives of this solution is to ensure that the most vulnerable population is protected from any negative impact of subsidy removal and at the same time, secure the necessary support required to make this happen.

Relationship between petrol price increases, inflation and cost of living

In Nigeria, the price of petrol is considered as a major driver of the cost of living, as it is

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used by all, including small businesses and many households given the unstable electricity supply. Therefore, any increase in fuel price could directly and immediately impact the prices of goods and services across the country. There is also the psychological impact that it tends to have because of the strong sentiment attached to cheap and affordable petrol. When petrol prices increase, small businesses tend to raise their prices to cover the increased cost of operation which can lead to higher prices for consumers. This can make it more difficult for people to afford basic necessities, lead to a decrease in the standard of living and contribute to poverty and inequality. However, previous attempts to remove the PMS subsidy had mostly been accompanied by hoarding and general scarcity which invariably amplified the impact of the price increase beyond just the subsidy removal.

Overall, the relationship between petrol price increases, inflation, and the cost of living in Nigeria is complex and multifaceted. While petrol price deregulation can contribute to higher costs of living and inflation, the impact can be moderated if complemented with effective policies and well-thought out implementation strategy.

Benefits of subsidy removal

We have examined the short to long term impact of the removal of fuel subsidy on the economy at large:

Short term

Reduces government borrowing and the associated huge deficit: Fuel subsidy has been a major source of government expenditure in Nigeria with huge sums being spent annually to keep petrol prices artificially low. This has led to the government borrowing heavily to finance the subsidy, which in turn increases the country's deficit. By removing the subsidy, the government can reduce its borrowing and the associated huge deficit, freeing up resources for other important sectors.

Free resources for investment in other critical sectors: With the removal of fuel subsidy, the government can free up resources that would have been spent on the subsidy to invest in other critical sectors such as education, healthcare, security and

infrastructure. This will not only improve the standard of living for citizens but will also enhance economic growth.

Reduce and remove incentive for smuggling and associated security risk: Subsidy has created a huge incentive for smuggling of fuel to neighbouring countries where they can be sold at higher prices. This has resulted in security risks as smuggling has also led to illegal refining, pipeline vandalism, and other criminal activities. By removing the subsidy, the incentive for smuggling will be reduced or eliminated which will lead to a reduction in security risks associated with fuel smuggling.

Long and medium term

Stronger Naira and decline in imported inflation: The massive importation of fuel increases the demand for foreign exchange. One of the medium to long term impacts of the subsidy removal is the reduction of fuel purportedly consumed in Nigeria as cheap, subsidized fuel will no longer be available for smuggling. This reduced volume will translate to a reduction in demand for foreign exchange which will lead to a stronger Naira. This will also reduce imported inflation and its pass-through effect, as the cost of importing petroleum products is a major contributor to inflation in Nigeria.

10 Empirical Verifications

i) **In an undergraduate class** conducted by one of the researchers of this study in Akwa Ibom State University, the students were challenged with a hypothesis that said, "Everybody in Nigeria does feel the impact of the fuel subsidy removal, because every household owns, at least a generator called, *I passed my neighbour* or a motor cycle". It was quite intelligent on the part of the students to politely object to that hypothesis with an argument that, some households in the rural communities, and even in urban centers do not even have the *I passed my neighbour* nor a motor cycles.

That argument got the lecturer to reframe the hypothesis to rather be that, "Majority of Nigeria does feel the impact of the fuel subsidy removal because every household, at least patronize the transport system in the country". The reframed hypothesis was accepted by both the lecturer and the students. The reason is because, at

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least, one person or more will have to travel, at least, on a motor bike or, if it is in the riverine area as our focus is based on, the inhabitant may be required to patronize the engine or speed boat to move from one place to another.

This fact goes to conform with the recently released multi-dimensional poverty report of the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), that Nigeria's poverty index was estimated to be at 0.257, with about 133 million people being multi-dimensionally poor. This category of individuals is not in a position to purchase vehicles or own generators that will run for several hours in the absence of power supply from the grid. The major touch point that they have with fuel consumption is indirectly through public transportation - and the majority of the vehicles that engage in public transportation run on AGO (diesel) which has already been deregulated.

ii) **At the motor park situated at Ikot Akpaden**, a town in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State where the famous Akwa Ibom State University is situated, a group of commuters, park workers, passengers, students and some business men and women were assembled for interview on the effect of fuel subsidy removal on their various businesses. The responses received were similar. While they all complain about the worst state of the Ikot Akpaden – Mkpato Enin – Ibekwe Akpanya road which, according to them, has for a long time forced them to divert and use alternative route through Awa in Onna Local Government Area to Etinan Local Government Area, then to Ekom Iman in Uyo, thereby causing a serious increase in transport fares. The passengers lamented that a trip that used to cost N600.00 and take a minimum of an hour now costs N2,000.00 and takes not less than two hours to reach the destination.

The students sympathized greatly with their parents who have to bear the brunt of providing the transport fares from time to time for their movement to and from school. The drivers on their part hinged on the high cost of fuel and spare parts to repair their vehicles and keep them running on the road and admitted, “we have no choice than to increase the fares in order to continue to buy fuel and stay in business”. The business men and women who also gathered at the researchers' interview also expressed their bitter experience on how their daily sales have dropped due to lack of money in the hands of people. According to them, “everybody is saving his money now for transport, while

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the vehicle owners and drivers save theirs for fuel, therefore, there is no more sales as it used to be before the fuel price increase”.

iii) **At Ibaka and Enwang fishing settlements** in Mbo Local Government Area of the State. At Ibaka (the host community of the proposed Ibom Deep Sea Port by Akwa Ibom State Government), a group of fishermen and women, buyers of fish and crayfish, boat paddlers, trolley drivers, and those who came for recreation or to while away time at the beach came around the interviewers who engaged them on this very matter of concern. Their responses were not quite deferent from what was gathered at Ikot Akpaden Motor park. But, the new things observed were that the fishermen and women lamented of the incessant effect of oil spillage from the oil companies on the aquatic lives on their waters.

Secondly, foreigners, strangers and non-indigenes were seen to have dominated the fishing ports and the fishing business entirely. Most of the trolleys that engaged in very enormous fishing tasks at the port were found to belong to Ghanaians, Niger Republic, etc. The indigenous fishermen were only scrambling for crayfish and periwinkles around the sea shores. Another alarming discovery was that most of the fishes were booked up front by bulk buyers and most of these bulk buyers of the fishes and crayfish were the Igbos. Little wonder it is often said that crayfish is cheaper at Aba than even at Ibaka. The huge number of the vehicles that were loading both fishes and crayfish were found to be moving to Aba, Umuahia, Owerri and Enugu. That was both a surprising and sad discovery, which informed the reason for the increase in the standard of living in that riverine area.

iv. **At Okorote, Iko and the environs in Eastern Obolo LGA.**, the situation was similar to that encountered at **Ukenkang, Mkpanak and the environs in Ibeno LGA.** These are very rich oil producing communities, but the two LGAs just like Enwang in Mbo local Government Area have only one access road, each leading to their local government headquarters. As said earlier, in Ibeno, Esit Eket, Eastern Obolo LGAs, there are no roads. Each of the three LGAs have only one access road which also serves as the exit route. Imagine what would happen if there should be any serious crisis in these places. Yet, there are oil companies' presence in these communities, including the conglomerate of Mobil Producing Nigeria Unlimited.

11 Discussion of Findings and Conclusion

According to Nnabugwu (2006), a conclusion must suffice that “the problem which motivated the research” has been solved, and “the objectives and hypotheses upheld”. Therefore, the issue of fuel subsidy removal has showed that Nigeria is a country that lives in paradox. This is, but an oil producing country where citizens are made to pay more for fuel which is found in abundance in their country. Successive government appeared adamant in the quest to remove fuel subsidy, while the people were equally resolved in its opposition to the removal of subsidy (Obasi, *et al.*, 2017). As such, previous governments could not implement that policy until the incumbent President Ahmed Bola Tinubu, who took a bold step on May 29, 2023, the very day of his swearing in to office as the President of Nigeria to announce the fuel subsidy removal. Since then, the economy of the country has taken a downward turn.

As a result of this, the above researchers took interest to embark on a participant research enquiry on Fuel Subsidy Removal Policy and its Toll on the Living Standard of Rural People of the Oil Producing Communities in Niger-Delta Region of Nigeria on the Gulf of Guinea, using Akwa Ibom State as the case study. In that circumstance, three null (Ho) hypotheses were postulated in order to enhance empirical verifications. Having embarked on a personal, one-on-one participatory and interactive study, those hypotheses were found thus:

i. There are some serious motivating factors of government towards implementing fuel subsidy removal policy at this critical moment in Nigeria. From our research, it is understood at the first instance that “*most key stakeholders agreed that the subsidy regime needs to go, it is clearly not sustainable in its current form*”. Secondly, successive governments in Nigeria had long intended to do away with the fuel subsidy due to series of allegations on the problems of middlemen, corruption and mismanagement of the administration of the policy. The Nigerian economy has been subsidized in various ways for many years and this includes fuel, education, electricity, forex, etc. Fuel subsidies began in the 1970s and became institutionalized in 1977, following the promulgation of the Price Control Act which made it illegal for some products (including petrol) to be sold above the regulated price. While the concept of

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subsidy itself is noble, its administration in Nigeria has been plagued with serious allegations of corruption and mismanagement (Blackgold, 2021).

ii. There are several resultant effects of fuel price hike on the lifestyle of the people of Akwa Ibom and State. The effects of the fuel subsidy removal on the people of Akwa

Ibom State is enormous and numerous. *Blackgold (2021)* further asserts that; any increase in fuel price could directly and immediately impact the prices of goods and services across the country. There is also the psychological impact that it tends to have because of the strong sentiment attached to cheap and affordable petrol. When petrol prices increase, small businesses tend to raise their prices to cover the increased cost of operation which can lead to higher prices for consumers. This can make it more difficult for people to afford basic necessities.

iii. It has been ascertained that the devaluation of the naira has affected the living standard of the rural people of Akwa Ibom State in Nigeria. Blackgold (2021) has succinctly captured this assumption in his earlier assertion;

In Nigeria, the price of petrol is considered as a major driver of the cost of living, as it is used by all including small businesses and many households given the unstable electricity supply. Therefore, any increase in fuel price could directly and immediately impact the prices of goods and services across the country.

12. Recommendations

i. The Federal Government should be transparent, fair and accountable to citizens in utilizing the huge sums of money (N400b) saved monthly by the Presidency from the commencement of the fuel subsidy removal. This will justify the fact that there were some serious motivating factors of government towards implementing fuel subsidy removal policy at this critical moment in Nigeria, which according to them, included serious allegations of corruption and mismanagement of subsidy funds.

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ii. Government should be deliberate to ensure that the several resultant effects of fuel price hike on the lifestyle of the people of Akwa Ibom State are removed totally, or at least, drastically stem down to the barest minimum. In other words, government should ensure that the most vulnerable population is protected from any negative impact of subsidy removal and at the same time secure the necessary support required to make this happen.

iii. The Federal Government should channel its energies to production and exportation of goods in order to stimulate and regulate foreign exchange earnings to boost the value of the naira, since it has been ascertained that the devaluation of the naira has affected the living standard of the rural people of Akwa Ibom State in Nigeria.

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